

Low-Temperature Electron Spin Resonance Study of MnPS₃ Antiferromagnetic Single Crystal

Fabrizio Moro,* Bing Wu, Iva Plutnarová, Jan Plutnar, and Zdenek Sofer*

Cite This: *J. Phys. Chem. C* 2024, 128, 19306–19312

Read Online

ACCESS |

Metrics & More

Article Recommendations

Supporting Information

ABSTRACT: van der Waals MnPS₃ compound belonging to the class of Néel-type antiferromagnets (AFM) has recently emerged as a promising two-dimensional material for spintronic applications. In this study, we report on the electron spin resonance (ESR) study of an MnPS₃ single crystal across the Néel transition temperature ($T_N = 78$ K) for the magnetic field applied in the directions parallel and perpendicular to the crystallographic c axis. Furthermore, the ESR angular dependence at a temperature near T_N has been investigated. We observed multiple resonance modes with antiferromagnetic, ferromagnetic, and paramagnetic characters. In addition, we revealed the occurrence of complex spin–spin correlations and a magnetic-topological Berezinskii–Kosterlitz–Thouless (BKT) phase transition (i.e., bound vortex–antivortex pairs) at T_{BKT} with T_{BKT}/T_N typically found in two-dimensional magnets.

1. INTRODUCTION

Layered van der Waals magnets, also referred to as 2D magnets, are gaining more and more interest because of their rich physical phenomena and potential applications in spintronics.^{1,2} Particularly appealing is the possibility to form heterostructures from mechanical exfoliation of bulk crystals down to few layers or even the monolayer. These heterostructures would be functional to realize magnetic tunneling junctions for spin-transfer torque (STT), spin-orbit torque (SOT), and thermally assisted (TA) magnetic random-access memories (MRAM), which are considered the only nonvolatile memories with high density, endurance, and fast writing speed.^{3,4}

The most widely studied 2D magnets are those with a ferromagnetic (FM) ground state,⁵ whereas research on antiferromagnetic (AFM) 2D magnets has not proceeded at the same pace mainly because of the difficulties in detecting detailed magnetic properties in materials with weak or null magnetization in the ground state. Nevertheless, several recent experiments have confirmed the possibility to store magnetic information with AFM materials.^{6–10} With respect to FM materials, AFM-based devices provide the advantage of avoiding unintentional magnetic *crossstalk* between neighboring devices because of zero stray fields. Thus, AFM 2D magnets would enable magnetic storage robust against magnetic field perturbations.⁷

Among the class of AFM 2D magnets, the MPS₃ (M = Fe, Ni, and Mn) family stands out because magnetic order, spin dimensionality, and transition temperature depend on M despite alike crystal structures. FePS₃ and NiPS₃ show zigzag-like AFM ordering, whereas MnPS₃ shows a Néel-type AFM

configuration where the spin of each magnetic site is antialigned with the two nearest neighbors.^{11–13} In the ordered state, FePS₃ and MnPS₃ show an easy axis perpendicular to the crystallographic plane, whereas NiPS₃ possesses an easy plane coinciding with the atomic planes.¹⁴ Furthermore, the bulk Néel temperatures for FePS₃,^{15–17} NiPS₃,¹⁸ and MnPS₃,¹⁴ are 118 K, 155 and 78 K, respectively.¹⁹

Despite the lower Néel temperature, MnPS₃ is particularly attractive because bulk-like magnetism might persist down to the monolayer limit,²⁰ as well as because of interesting phenomena such as induced ferromagnetism²¹ and spin flop transition¹³ at low temperature in the presence of magnetic field. Recently, the possibility to observe a magnetic-topological Berezinskii–Kosterlitz–Thouless (BKT) phase transition, which stabilizes a bound vortex–antivortex pair at BKT temperature, T_{BKT} , has been suggested.^{22,23}

Nevertheless, a distinction must be made between type-A layered AFMs, which possess ferromagnetic coupling within the layers, and Néel-layered AFMs in which spins are arranged antiferromagnetically within each layer. In the former, magnetic tunneling junctions can be realized by changing the relative orientation between the layers. In the latter, spin-

Received: September 12, 2024

Revised: October 12, 2024

Accepted: October 15, 2024

Published: October 25, 2024

Figure 1. (a) Crystal structure of MnPS_3 . (b) EDS mapping indicating the elemental distribution of Mn, P, and S within MnPS_3 . (c) TEM image and corresponding high-resolution TEM image with an inset showing the lattice fringe spacing. (d) SAED pattern and (e) the $[001]$ zone axis of MnPS_3 .

filtering effects do not occur and the magnetic properties cannot be monitored with conventional transport measurements.²⁰ Therefore, the magnetic characterization of Néel-layered AFMs requires alternative techniques. Electron spin resonance (ESR) and the related electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR), antiferromagnetic resonance (AMR), and ferromagnetic resonance (FMR) techniques have been proved to be powerful tools to study 2D magnets.²⁴ Temperature magnetic resonance field, linewidth, and intensity enable the characterization of the magnetic transition phases, whereas the angular dependence of the magnetic resonances in a single crystal provides unambiguous determination of the magnetic axes. Recently, ESR has shown to be a valid tool to assess the spin dimensionality and find signatures for magnetic topological phase transitions of 2D magnets in the bulk 3D form from combined angular and temperature dependences of the spectral linewidth supported by theoretical modeling.^{25,26} This is possible because 2D magnets possess very weak interlayer magnetic coupling relative to the in-plane coupling, which makes them inherently 2D even in their bulk form.

Previous ESR studies on MnPS_3 have been reported by a few groups at conventional X-band frequency²³ as well as at frequencies in the 8–330 GHz frequency range.^{22,27} The high frequencies/strong magnetic fields studies have reported the occurrence of AFM and paramagnetic resonance branches^{22,27} as well as the occurrence of a transition from 3D-like character of the spin wave excitation to a 2D-XY scaling regime boosted by the strong magnetic field.²² Whereas, at X-band, only a single broad line has been reported in the temperature region above the Néel temperature ($T > 100$ K).^{23,28,29}

Here, we investigate the temperature and angular dependence of the ESR spectra on an MnPS_3 single crystal in the relevant temperature range crossing T_N from room temperature to liquid helium temperature. Our ESR spectra show the occurrence of previously unreported resonance branches above the transition temperature $T_N = 78$ K, revealing a complex magnetic behavior of MnPS_3 with mixed ferromagnetic and antiferromagnetic phases, which could be responsible for the formation of magnetic topological phases. Finally, we discuss and interpret the ESR based on the BKT model of the ESR linewidth.

2. METHODS

2.1. Crystal Synthesis.

MnPS_3 was made by direct reaction in ampule from elements with subsequent chemical vapor transport crystal growth.^{30,31} Manganese (99.95%, –100 mesh, Mateck, Germany), phosphorus (99.9999%, 2–6 mm granules, Wuhan Xinrong New Materials Co., China), and sulfur (99.9999%, 2–6 mm granules, Wuhan Xinrong New Materials Co., China) were placed in a quartz ampule (50 × 250 mm) in a stoichiometric ratio corresponding to 30 g of MnPS_3 . To facilitate chemical vapor transport, sulfur and phosphorus were used in 1 % excess together with 0.5 g of iodine (99.9%, Fisher Scientific, USA). The ampule was sealed under high vacuum using oxygen–hydrogen welding torch and diffusion pump with liquid nitrogen trap (pressure $< 1 \times 10^{-3}$ Pa). The ampule was placed in a muffle furnace and heated at 450 °C for 50 h and subsequently in steps at 500 °C for 50 h, 600 °C for 50 h, and 700 °C for 50 h. The heating rate between each step was 0.2 °C/min. Subsequently, the ampule

was placed in a two-zone furnace for crystal growth. First, the growth zone was heated at 750 °C and the source zone at 500 °C. After 2 days, the gradient was reversed, and the source zone was heated at 750 °C, while the growth zone temperature was decreased from 700 to 650 °C over a period of 5 days, and for the following 5 days, the growth zone was kept at 650 °C. At the end of crystal growth procedure, the growth zone was heated at 350 °C, while the source zone was kept at 150 °C for 2 h. The ampule was opened in an argon-filled glovebox, where crystals with size over 1 cm were separated. The resulting bulk MnPS₃ crystals are air stable and do not need any protection layer. For the measurement, no protection layer was needed and crystals could be handled on air. Exfoliated layers are more susceptible to degradation by air humidity and should be handled on air only for a short time. In ambient atmosphere, MnPS₃ can be safely handled up to at least 100 °C.

2.2. X-ray Diffraction (XRD). The crystal structure was characterized using an X-ray diffractometer (XRD, Bruker D8 with Cu K α radiation, Germany) and Raman analysis (using a 532 nm laser, Renishaw, England), and transmission electron microscopy (TEM, EFTEM Jeol 2200 FS microscope, Japan).

2.3. X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS). The surface composition of the samples was further studied with X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) using a SPECS spectrometer equipped with a monochromatic Al K α X-ray source (1486.7 eV) and a hemispherical electron analyzer Phoibos 150. The survey spectra were recorded with energy E_p set to 100 eV and the high-resolution spectra of the core lines with E_p set to 20 eV. The base chamber pressure during the acquisitions was at 10⁻⁹ mbar or lower. Due to a heavy charge development on the surfaces of samples, a low-energy electron flow generated by an electron flood gun has been used to compensate the charge buildup.

2.4. Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM). TEM, including high-resolution TEM and SAED, was recorded on an EFTEM Jeol 2200 FS microscope, Japan. Energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) analysis was also conducted using a detector from Oxford Instruments in the same instrument.

2.5. Raman analysis. The Raman resonance spectra were recorded using a confocal Raman microscope (Renishaw, UK) with a DPSS Nd:YAG laser (532 nm), 20 \times lens, 0.5 mW on sample (1%), 20 s exposure time, and 30 scans.

2.6. Electron Spin Resonance. Samples were mounted on a Suprasil quartz rod and into a goniometer with 1/2 degree sensitivity for ESR crystal rotation measurements. A flat crystal with surface size 2 \times 3 mm² and thickness <1 mm was selected to avoid saturation and distortion of the ESR signal. The ESR spectra were recorded with a Varian E15 spectrometer coupled to a Bruker super high Q cavity operated at X-band (~9.4 GHz). The static magnetic field was modulated at 100 kHz with a modulation amplitude of 4 G. The magnetic field was continuously monitored with an electronic counter and a Hall probe. Sample temperatures in the range 4–300 K were obtained with an Oxford ESR 900 cryostat. A DPPH sample was used as a reference to determine the g -factors. MatLab-generated routines were used to fit the spectra. Peak-to-peak linewidths ΔH were calculated from the full-width half-maximum $\Delta H_{1/2}$ obtained from the Lorentzian fit with the relation: $\Delta H = \Delta H_{1/2}/\sqrt{3}$.

3. RESULTS

The X-ray diffraction (XRD) structure of MnPS₃ is shown in Figure 1a. The diffraction pattern presented in Figure S1 indicates high crystalline quality and a well-ordered structure of the MnPS₃ single crystal with C2/ m space group. EDS mapping images shown in Figure 1b provide a spatial distribution of manganese (Mn), phosphorus (P), and sulfur (S) within the sample, confirming the homogeneous composition and elemental distribution across the crystal. The corresponding EDS spectrum of MnPS₃ in Figure S2 shows the ratio of Mn:P:S in weight is 14.8%:8.4%:25.6%, corresponding to the atomic ratio of 1.0:1.01:2.96, matching well with the designed stoichiometric ratio of the compound's formula. High-resolution TEM (HRTEM) reveals the atomic lattice with a measured lattice spacing (d) of 3.57 Å for the (111) planes, consistent with known crystallographic data for MnPS₃ (Figure 1c,d). The SAED pattern displays sharp and well-defined diffraction spots, confirming the crystal direction as [001] and indicating high crystallinity and structural integrity (Figure 1e). These results are also supported by additional XPS and Raman studies reported in Figures S3 and S4.

Figure 2 shows the temperature dependence of the ESR spectra recorded for the external magnetic field parallel ($H\parallel c$)

Figure 2. ESR spectra recorded as a function of the temperature for $H\parallel c$ (a) and $H\perp c$ (b). The dashed lines are guide for the eyes to single out the different resonance lines: PM, mode I, and mode II.

and perpendicular ($H\perp c$) to the crystallographic c axis. In both cases, there is a single ESR peak centered at $H_r = 342$ mT and $H_r = 339$ mT, respectively, whose resonance fields are essentially independent of temperature. We refer to the central resonance peak as PM due to its paramagnetic behavior, as discussed further. Upon cooling for $H\parallel c$ we observe the emergence of a secondary resonance branch that overlaps with the PM signal at $T \sim 150$ K, and it evolves down to $T \sim 50$ K. Hereafter, we refer to this signal as mode I. For $T < 94$ K another resonance signal, mode II, appears from very low magnetic field values.

For $H\perp c$, only one resonance signal is observed down to $T \sim 50$ K with a weak contribution from mode I appearing for $T \sim 100$ K.

We extracted the ESR intensity, resonance peak (H_r), and peak-to-peak linewidth (ΔH) as a function of temperature and rotation for $H\parallel c$ and $H\perp c$ from fitting of the spectra to Lorentzian functions.

Figure 3. ESR spectra recorded for $H \perp c$ and $H \parallel c$ for $T \sim 75$ K (a) and $T \sim 85$ K (b). Black curves are experimental data, and red curves are the simulations. Spectra are offset along the vertical axes for clarity.

Figure 4. Temperature dependence of the ESR intensity (a), peak-to-peak linewidth (b) for the PM and mode II resonances for $H \perp c$ and $H \parallel c$. In (b), dashed lines are fittings of the data to the BKT model. Resonance fields are for $H \perp c$ (c) and $H \parallel c$ (d). Line are guides for the eyes.

In Figure 3 are reported stack plots of the simulation and the experimental data for the canonical orientations and for two representative temperatures, namely, $T = 75$ K and $T = 85$ K.

We now describe in detail the temperature dependence of PM and *mode I* and *mode II* reported in Figure 4. PM intensity for $H \parallel c$ increases by lowering the temperature to $T \sim 130$ K before decreasing at lower temperatures. *Mode I* intensity decreases monotonously from room temperature to $T \sim 80$ K. For $T < 100$ K, the *mode II* emerges with a rapidly increasing intensity, reaching a maximum at $T \sim 74$ K before quickly decreasing at lower temperatures. PM intensity for $H \perp c$

increases by lowering the temperature down to $T \sim 120$ K before decreasing at lower temperatures and vanishing for $T < 100$ K.

The resonance field for PM is essentially independent of temperature for both orientations $H \parallel c$ and $H \perp c$, whereas its resonance linewidth ΔH increases monotonously upon cooling until $T \sim 150$ K, and at lower temperatures, it rapidly broadens for $T < 100$ K. Resonance field for *mode I* for both $H \perp c$ and $H \parallel c$ separates from PM for $T < 150$ K and shifts to lower fields, reaching a minimum for $T \sim 100$ K before shifting to higher resonance fields. The resonance field of *mode II* for $H \parallel c$

Figure 5. Angular dependence of the resonance field (a) and ESR linewidth (b) for the PM and *mode II* ESR signals for $T = 75$ K.

appears from the zero field at $T < 100$ K and shifts linearly to higher magnetic fields.

The angular dependence of the resonance field, H_r , and peak-to-peak linewidth, ΔH , obtained from the best fit at $T = 75$ K for PM and *mode II* are reported in Figure 5. H_r and ΔH for the PM signal depend weakly on the orientation of the crystal with respect to the magnetic field, whereas a pronounced angular dependence is observed for *mode II*. H_r and ΔH show a minimum for $H||c$ and a maximum for $H\perp c$.

4. DISCUSSION

The observed PM signal is associated with a paramagnetic phase in the MnPS_3 crystal because it is isotropic and its resonance field is essentially temperature independent. This interpretation is also supported by the analysis of its ESR intensity, which increases for lower temperatures in agreement with the Curie's law for paramagnets. The decrease in the ESR intensity for $T < 150$ K indicates the onset of an antiferromagnetic phase, where the antiparallel alignment of the Mn spins effectively decreases the magnetic susceptibility. The shift of *mode I* to lower and higher fields in the temperature region 150–90 K (Figure 4c,d) suggests the occurrence of mixed antiferromagnetic and ferromagnetic phases. The last one is supported by *mode II*, which appears from zero magnetic field at $T \sim 90$ K, corresponding to the temperature upturn of *mode I*. For $T < 90$ K *mode II* shifts quickly to high fields at lower temperatures, thus suggesting its AFM nature further corroborated by the quenching of its ESR intensity. These results elucidate the complex mixing of AFM and FM where the degree of mixing might give rise to different spin arrangements.

The van der Waals nature of MnPS_3 crystals suggests that magnetic order could be confined in a 2-dimensional space and described by the XY spin model below the magnetic phase transition. Within such a model, topological effects can lead to the formation of local spin arrangements such as bound vortex and antivortex pairs, as predicted by the BKT theory. The ESR spectra can capture the signature of the BKT transition in both the temperature and angular dependence of the ESR linewidth. The ESR linewidth follows the temperature dependence according to the BKT model:³²

$$\Delta H(T) = \Delta H_{\infty} \exp\left(\frac{3b}{\sqrt{\frac{T}{T_{\text{BKT}}} - 1}}\right) + \Delta H_0 \quad (1)$$

where in the first term, ΔH_{∞} is the linewidth to infinity, $b = \pi/2$, and ΔH_0 takes into account an offset of the room temperature linewidth (Table 1).

Table 1. Results of the Fitting to eq 1

BKT model	ΔH_{∞} (mT)	b	ΔH_0 (mT)	T_{BKT} (K)
$H c$	4 ± 1	$\pi/2$	183 ± 10	28 ± 1
$H\perp c$	17 ± 5	$\pi/2$	170 ± 20	25 ± 3

From the fitting of the data in Figure 3b, we find a substantial agreement between the T_{BKT} obtained for both orientations within the fitting error bars. The value of T_{BKT} is always below the magnetic ordering temperature T_N , with a ratio $\frac{T_{\text{BKT}}}{T_N} \sim 0.47 - 0.48$, as typically found in quasi-two-dimensional magnets.²⁶

The angular dependence of the resonance field and linewidth of the PM resonance below $T \sim 90$ K is very weak, confirming its isotropic character in the entire temperature range investigated. A pronounced ESR angular dependence is observed for *mode II*. In order to search for the formation of bound vortex and antivortex pairs, we fit the ESR resonance linewidth angular dependence of *mode II* at $T = 75$ K. Experimental evidence indicates that the ESR linewidth in the regime of mixed FM and AFM phases, which is responsible for the formation of topological phases, deviates from a simple $\cos^2\varphi$ dependence:

$$\Delta H(\varphi) = A(3\cos^2\varphi - 1) + \Delta H_{0||} \quad (2a)$$

Instead, it assumes what it is usually referred to as a W -like shape, which can be fitted with the following equation:

$$\Delta H(\varphi) = B(3\cos^2\varphi - 1)^2 + \Delta H_{0\perp} \quad (2b)$$

The fitting of the ESR linewidth to eq 2a suggests the occurrence of only one dominant magnetic phase (i.e., FM), whereas the ESR linewidth at $T = 75$ K clearly deviates from a $\cos^2\varphi$ -like shape leaning more toward a W -like shape. This argument is supported by the fitting of the data to eq 2b with parameters: $B = 153 \pm 7$ mT and $\Delta H_{0\perp} = 22 \pm 6$ mT.

5. CONCLUSION

We have reported on a temperature and angular study of an MnPS_3 single crystal by ESR at conventional X-band frequency. We have observed the occurrence of a paramagnetic phase along with multiple resonance modes above and below

the Néel temperature for both the magnetic field applied along and perpendicular to the crystallographic c axis. We have ascribed these modes to competing AFM and FM interactions, as suggested by their opposite shift of the resonance fields. From the analysis of the resonance linewidth, we have obtained evidence for spin–spin correlations at $T < T_N$, which we ascribe to the magnetic topological phase transition and to the formation of bound vortex and antivortex pairs of the BKT model.

■ ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Data Availability Statement

The datasets generated during and/or analyzed during the study are accessible via the Zenodo repository: <https://zenodo.org/records/13692266> and Biccoca Open Archive Research Data, doi: 10.17632/x7zhjtzy5s.1.

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge at <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.jpcc.4c06156>.

XRD studies, EDS spectrum of MnPS_3 , XPS characterization, and Raman studies (PDF)

■ AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding Authors

Fabrizio Moro – Department of Materials Science, University of Milano-Bicocca, Milano 20125, Italy; orcid.org/0000-0002-6381-0479; Email: fabrizio.moro@unimib.it

Zdenek Sofer – Department of Inorganic Chemistry, Faculty of Chemical Technology, University of Chemistry and Technology Prague, 166 28 Prague 6, Czech Republic; Email: zdenek.sofer@seznam.cz

Authors

Bing Wu – Department of Inorganic Chemistry, Faculty of Chemical Technology, University of Chemistry and Technology Prague, 166 28 Prague 6, Czech Republic

Iva Plutnarová – Department of Inorganic Chemistry, Faculty of Chemical Technology, University of Chemistry and Technology Prague, 166 28 Prague 6, Czech Republic

Jan Plutnar – Department of Inorganic Chemistry, Faculty of Chemical Technology, University of Chemistry and Technology Prague, 166 28 Prague 6, Czech Republic

Complete contact information is available at: <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.jpcc.4c06156>

Author Contributions

I.P. and Z.S. prepared the MnPS_3 crystals and performed the XRD study and Raman analysis; J.P. performed the XPS analysis and interpretation. B.W. performed SEM and TEM analyses. Z.S. secured research funding and resources. F.M. collected and analyzed the ESR data and wrote the manuscript with contributions from all the authors.

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

■ ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Z.S. was supported by the ERC-CZ program (project LL2101) from the Ministry of Education Youth and Sports (MEYS). The authors acknowledge the assistance provided by the Advanced Multiscale Materials for Key Enabling Technologies project, supported by the Ministry of Education, Youth, and Sports of the Czech Republic (project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/

22_008/0004558) cofunded by the European Union. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant agreement ID 101135196.

■ REFERENCES

- (1) Jiang, X.; Liu, Q.; Xing, J.; Liu, N.; Guo, Y.; Liu, Z.; Zhao, J. Recent progress on 2D magnets: Fundamental mechanism, structural design and modification. *Appl. Phys. Rev.* **2021**, *8* (3), 031305.
- (2) Gibertini, M.; Koperski, M.; Morpurgo, A. F.; Novoselov, K. S. Magnetic 2D materials and heterostructures. *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **2019**, *14* (5), 408–419.
- (3) Bhatti, S.; Sbiaa, R.; Hirohata, A.; Ohno, H.; Fukami, S.; Piramanayagam, S. N. Spintronics based random access memory: a review. *Mater. Today* **2017**, *20* (9), 530–548.
- (4) Yang, H.; Valenzuela, S. O.; Chshiev, M.; Couet, S.; Dieny, B.; Dlubak, B.; Fert, A.; Garello, K.; Jamet, M.; Jeong, D. E. Two-dimensional materials prospects for non-volatile spintronic memories. *Nature* **2022**, *606* (7915), 663–673.
- (5) Papavasileiou, A. V.; Menelaou, M.; Sarkar, K. J.; Sofer, Z.; Polavarapu, L.; Mourdikoudis, S. Ferromagnetic elements in two-dimensional materials: 2D magnets and beyond. *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2024**, *34* (2), 2309046.
- (6) Loth, S.; Baumann, S.; Lutz, C. P.; Eigler, D. M.; Heinrich, A. J. Bistability in Atomic-Scale Antiferromagnets. *Science* **2012**, *335* (6065), 196–199.
- (7) Marti, X.; Fina, I.; Frontera, C.; Liu, J.; Wadley, P.; He, Q.; Paull, R. J.; Clarkson, J. D.; Kudrnovsky, J.; Turek, I. Room-temperature antiferromagnetic memory resistor. *Nat. Mater.* **2014**, *13* (4), 367–374.
- (8) Moriyama, T.; Matsuzaki, N.; Kim, K.-J.; Suzuki, I.; Taniyama, T.; Ono, T. Sequential write-read operations in FeRh antiferromagnetic memory. *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2015**, *107* (12), 122403.
- (9) Park, B. G.; Wunderlich, J.; Martí, X.; Holy, V.; Kurosaki, Y.; Yamada, M.; Yamamoto, H.; Nishide, A.; Hayakawa, J.; Takahashi, H. A spin-valve-like magnetoresistance of an antiferromagnet-based tunnel junction. *Nat. Mater.* **2011**, *10* (5), 347–351.
- (10) Wadley, P.; Howells, B.; Železný, J.; Andrews, C.; Hills, V.; Campion, R. P.; Novák, V.; Olejník, K.; Maccheronzi, F.; Dhesi, S. S. Electrical switching of an antiferromagnet. *Science* **2016**, *351* (6273), 587–590.
- (11) Huang, B.; McGuire, M. A.; May, A. F.; Xiao, D.; Jarillo-Herrero, P.; Xu, X. D. Emergent phenomena and proximity effects in two-dimensional magnets and heterostructures. *Nat. Mater.* **2020**, *19* (12), 1276–1289.
- (12) Leflem, G.; Brec, R.; Ouvard, G.; Louisy, A.; Segransan, P. Magnetic interactions in the layer compounds MPX_3 ($M = \text{Mn, Fe, Ni}$; $X = \text{S, Se}$). *J. Phys. Chem. Solids* **1982**, *43* (5), 455–461.
- (13) Goossens, D. J.; Wildes, A. R.; Ritter, C.; Hicks, T. J. Ordering and the nature of the spin flop phase transition in MnPS_3 . *J. Phys.: Condens. Matter* **2000**, *12* (8), 1845.
- (14) Joy, P. A.; Vasudevan, S. Magnetism in the layered transition-metal thiophosphates MPS_3 ($M = \text{Mn, Fe, and Ni}$). *Phys. Rev. B* **1992**, *46* (9), 5425–5433.
- (15) Jernberg, P.; Bjarman, S.; Wappling, R. FePS_3 - a 1ST-order-phase transition in a 2D Ising antiferromagnet. *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* **1984**, *46* (1–2), 178–190.
- (16) Rule, K. C.; McIntyre, G. J.; Kennedy, S. J.; Hicks, T. J. Single-crystal and powder neutron diffraction experiments on FePS_3 : Search for the magnetic structure. *Phys. Rev. B* **2007**, *76* (13), 134402.
- (17) Susner, M. A.; Chyasnachyus, M.; McGuire, M. A.; Ganesh, P.; Maksymovych, P. Metal thio- and selenophosphates as multifunctional van der Waals layered materials. *Adv. Mater.* **2017**, *29* (38), 1602852.
- (18) Wildes, A. R.; Simonet, V.; Ressouche, E.; McIntyre, G. J.; Avdeev, M.; Suard, E.; Kimber, S. A. J.; Langon, D.; Pepe, G.; Moubaraki, B. Magnetic structure of the quasi-two-dimensional antiferromagnet NiPS_3 . *Phys. Rev. B* **2015**, *92* (22), 224408.

- (19) Yin, T. *Novel Light-Matter Interactions in 2D Magnets*; IntechOpen, 2023.
- (20) Long, G.; Henck, H.; Gibertini, M.; Dumcenco, D.; Wang, Z.; Taniguchi, T.; Watanabe, K.; Giannini, E.; Morpurgo, A. F. Persistence of magnetism in atomically thin MnPS₃ crystals. *Nano Lett.* **2020**, *20* (4), 2452–2459.
- (21) Han, H.; Lin, H.; Gan, W.; Xiao, R.; Liu, Y.; Ye, J.; Chen, L.; Wang, W.; Zhang, L.; Zhang, C. Field-induced spin reorientation in the Néel-type antiferromagnet MnPS₃. *Phys. Rev. B* **2023**, *107* (7), 075423.
- (22) Abraham, J. J.; Senyk, Y.; Shemerliuk, Y.; Selter, S.; Aswartham, S.; Büchner, B.; Kataev, V.; Alfonsov, A. Magnetic anisotropy and low-energy spin dynamics in the van der Waals compounds Mn₂P₂S₃ and MnNiP₂S₆. *Phys. Rev. B* **2023**, *107* (16), 165141.
- (23) Chaudhuri, S.; Kuo, C. N.; Chen, Y. S.; Lue, C. S.; Lin, J. G. Low-temperature magnetic order rearrangement in the layered van der Waals compound MnPS₃. *Phys. Rev. B* **2022**, *106* (9), 094416.
- (24) Kataev, V.; Büchner, B.; Alfonsov, A. Electron spin resonance spectroscopy on magnetic van der Waals compounds. *Appl. Magn. Reson.* **2024**, *55*, 923–960.
- (25) Hemmida, M.; Krug von Nidda, H.-A.; Loidl, A. Traces of Z₂-vortices in CuCrO₂, AgCrO₂, and PdCrO₂. *J. Phys. Soc. Jpn.* **2011**, *80* (5), 053707.
- (26) Hemmida, M.; Winterhalter-Stocker, N.; Ehlers, D.; Von Nidda, H. A. K.; Yao, M.; Bannies, J.; Rienks, E. D. L.; Kurlito, R.; Felser, C.; Büchner, B. Topological magnetic order and superconductivity in EuRbFe₄As₄. *Phys. Rev. B* **2021**, *103* (19), 195112.
- (27) Kobets, M. I.; Dergachev, K. G.; Gnatchenko, S. L.; Khats'ko, E. N.; Vysochanskii, Y. M.; Gurzan, M. I. Antiferromagnetic resonance in Mn₂P₂S₆. *Low-Temp. Phys.* **2009**, *35* (12), 930–934.
- (28) Okuda, K.; Kurosawa, K.; Saito, S.; Honda, M.; Yu, Z.; Date, M. Magnetic properties of layered compound MnPS₃. *J. Phys. Soc. Jpn.* **1986**, *55* (12), 4456–4463.
- (29) Joy, P. A.; Vasudevan, S. Magnetism and spin dynamics in MnPS₃ and pyridine intercalated MnPS₃ - an electron paramagnetic resonance study. *J. Chem. Phys.* **1993**, *99* (6), 4411–4422.
- (30) Bronger, W.; Hardtdegen, H.; Kanert, M.; Müller, P.; Schmitz, D. Alkali metal manganese selenides and tellurides - Synthesis, crystal and spin structures. *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.* **1996**, *622* (2), 313–318.
- (31) Hardtdegen, H.; Mikulics, M.; Riess, S.; Schuck, M.; Saltzmann, T.; Simon, U.; Longo, M. Modern chemical synthesis methods towards low-dimensional phase change structures in the Ge-Sb-Te material system. *Prog. Cryst. Growth Charact. Mater.* **2015**, *61* (2–4), 27–45.
- (32) Heinrich, M.; Krug von Nidda, H. A.; Loidl, A.; Rogado, N.; Cava, R. J. Potential signature of a Kosterlitz-Thouless transition in BaNi₂V₂O₈. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **2003**, *91* (13), 137601.